

Theory of chronocoulometry of a pseudo first-order catalytic process at a rough electrode[†]

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Manuscript received 25 October 2017, accepted 01 November 2017

Abstract : A theoretical model for single potential step charge-transients has been developed for the pseudo first-order catalytic coupled (EC') reaction mechanism at rough electrode-electrolyte interface. A second-order perturbation solution in surface prole for an arbitrary rough surface is obtained. The expression for the charge-transient at the rough electrode-electrolyte interface for band limited self-affine fractal roughness is obtained. An extension of the generalized Danckwerts' expression in terms of the charge is presented. Our results show an enhancement in the charge-transients due to the roughness present at the electrode surface. The morphological characteristics show strong dependency in the anomalous intermediate regime obtained from the power-spectrum of roughness while the long-time regime is the time dependent kinetic controlled. The traditional plot of charge-transient does not provide the information related to the morphology and its possible kinetic influences.

Keywords : Power spectrum of roughness, fractal electrode, Chronocoulometry, catalytic process, charge transfer.

Introduction

The surface morphology or roughness of an electrode affects the spectroelectrochemical responses. The roughness effect is inevitable especially, if the electrodes are made of solid materials. The rough electrodes have potential to be used in fundamental and applied fields¹⁻⁶. This is possible because rough surfaces show enhanced surface reactions due to the increase in the effective area. Rough surface is also capable to separate electrons and holes from combination because of generation of channel-like structure in the vicinity of the electrode. Hence, rough electrode surface structure is favorable to enhance the performance of light emitting diodes and solar cell devices¹.

In our previous paper, we have generalized the Anson equation that describes the potentiostatic response of a reversible charge transfer reaction for

rough electrode. It explains the observed deviation in the Anson plot from linearity due to the roughness present at the electrode surface⁷. An important reaction mechanism is where the electrochemical step is coupled with bulk kinetics which is the catalytic coupled reaction mechanism used in many fundamental as well as in applied fields^{8-10,12-21}. Saveant *et al.*⁹ discussed the potentiostatic and cyclic voltammetric responses of this mechanism through various zones attributing to the extent or reversibility of the E step as well as the dependence of the response on the concentration of the electrochemically inactive species. Here, we focus on the influence of ubiquitous electrode roughness on the response of such pseudo first-order catalytic coupled reaction mechanism under the potentiostatic perturbation.

The pseudo first-order catalytic-coupled (EC') reaction mechanism scheme is one of the most impor-

[†]Acharya J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture (2016).

tant class of catalytic coupled reaction which is represented as⁸⁻¹⁰ :

where k is homogeneous rate constant, z and z' are electrochemically inactive at the electrode potential at which reaction proceeds. The first step is the reversible redox reaction at the electrode surface and the second step is the chemically coupled reaction with the first step.

Chronocoulometry is an effective technique for studying homogeneous chemical reactions that are coupled to the heterogeneous electron transfer reaction. It is well known that, the chronocoulometry technique is advantageous over chronoamperometry²². The studies such as²² : mechanism, rate constant, faradaic and non-faradaic components separation, adsorption studies²³⁻²⁸ can be easily done by using chronocoulometric technique. The chronocoulometric study for EC' reaction mechanism was first done by J. H. Christie in 1967 for the condition of double potential-step²⁹. He proposed an expression for the charge-transient for the pseudo first-order EC' reac-

tion mechanism for single-step also at smooth electrode, which can be written as²⁹ :

$$Q_C(t) = Q_P(t) \left(\frac{2\sqrt{kt} e^{kt} + \sqrt{\pi}(1+2kt)\text{erf}(\sqrt{kt})}{4\sqrt{kt}} \right), \quad (2)$$

where $Q_C(t)$ is the total catalytic charge-transient, t is the time, and "erf" is the error function³⁰. $Q_P(t)$ is the potentiostatic charge-transient for planar surface which is given by the Anson and is known as Anson equation²² :

$$Q_P(t) = \frac{2nF A_0 C_s \sqrt{Dt}}{\sqrt{\pi}}, \quad (3)$$

where D is the diffusion co-efficient of the species, n is the number of electron(s) involved in the redox reaction, F is Faraday constant, A_0 is the electrode geometric area and C_s is the bulk concentration of the species. This pioneer work of Christie²⁹ has given a basis to study many aspects of catalytic coupled reaction mechanism by using chronocoulometry technique.

The recent contribution in theoretical and experimental studies in EC' mechanism such as to determine the kinetic parameters of EC' mechanism in square wave voltammetry (SWV)^{31,32} and its surface catalytic mechanism³³, analysis of two-step redox mechanisms in protein-film by cyclic staircase voltammetry (SCV)³⁴ and comparative study of mechanism by SWV and SCV³⁵ are significant and further explored the understanding of EC' mechanism.

The recent interest in realistic fractal geometry which use the power spectrum of roughness approach, has opened a new horizon to understand the influence of surface disorder on spectroelectrochemical responses. This includes the localization phenomenon of impedance on a Weierstrass fractal surface³⁶, anomalous electric double-layer dynamics in ionic liquids³⁷, anomalous response in cyclic staircase voltammetry³⁸, generalization of Randles-Ershler admittance for an arbitrary topography electrode³⁹, double potential step chronoamperometry response for

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of EC' reaction mechanism taking place at a rough electrode-electrolyte interface. The various morphological and phenomenological characteristics are shown. The various characteristics are as : D_H is fractal dimension, ℓ_t is width of the interface, ℓ and L are lower and upper cut-off length scales, respectively. \sqrt{Dt} is diffusion-width, $\sqrt{D/k}$ is the reaction layer thickness and k is the homogeneous rate constant. Here z is the catalyst which is inactive at the potential at which reaction is occurring.

finite fractal and nonfractal electrode roughness with and without ohmic effect⁴⁰, dynamics of the electric double layer at a heterogeneous and rough electrode⁴¹, absorbance-transient for pseudo first-order catalytic coupled mechanism⁴², generalization of Gouy-Chapman-Stern model for a morphologically complex electrode⁴³, Debye-Falkenhagen Dynamics⁴⁴ and others⁴⁵⁻⁵⁰.

Chronocoulometry and chronoabsorptometry show linear relationship to each other and have mathematical isomorphism^{22,51}. Absorbance is the characteristic of the integrated concentration of a given species whereas, charge represents the integrated flux of the species at the electrode surface. Thus, the influence of the kinetic process occurring in the diffusion layer on absorbance-time behavior is quite different from that of the charge-time⁵². Hence, it is of great importance to analyze the problem from chronocoulometric point of view also, along with the chronoabsorptometry method⁴². Due to the mathematical isomorphism between these two techniques, the detailed calculations are not provided here and the formalism of the problem can be found in Ref. 35.

The present paper is organized as follows : in the first section, the charge transient is obtained for an EC' reaction mechanism at an arbitrary and random roughness profile, in the second section, the chronocoulometric expression for an EC' reaction mechanism at finite self-affine fractal rough electrode is obtained followed by the results and discussion. Finally, on the basis of results and discussion, conclusions are drawn.

EC' reaction mechanism at random rough electrodes

In this section, the chronocoulometric model for an EC' reaction mechanism at random rough electrode is obtained. The random morphology of the rough electrode surface or interface can be satisfactorily described as centered Gaussian fields which is statistically homogeneous surface $\zeta(\vec{r}_{\parallel})$, where \vec{r}_{\parallel} is a two dimensional space vector. The surface struc-

ture factor is used to understand the statistics for such Gaussian fields or surfaces. The surface structure factor is defined as the Fourier transform of the surface correlation function^{53,54} and is given as : $\langle |\hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{\parallel})|^2 \rangle$, where \vec{K}_{\parallel} is the wave-vector in two dimension and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ represents the ensemble average. It is also known as the power-spectrum of roughness and is quantified as the ensemble average over all the possible configurations. The equation which governs the ensemble averaged Fourier transformed surface profile and its correlation is given as :

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{\parallel}) \rangle &= 0 \\ \langle \zeta(\vec{K}_{\parallel}) \zeta(\vec{K}_{\parallel}') \rangle &= (2\pi)^2 \delta(\vec{K}_{\parallel} + \vec{K}_{\parallel}') \langle |\zeta(\vec{K}_{\parallel})|^2 \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\delta(\vec{K}_{\parallel})$ is the Dirac delta function in \vec{K}_{\parallel} .

The realistic finite fractal concept is used to characterize the roughness of the electrode surface. The finite fractals have two cut-off length scales, i.e. lower and upper cut-off length scales and the range of these two cut-off lengths show self-affine fractal behavior. The upper cut-off length scale is nothing but the correlation length. The fractals without these band limited cut-off length scales are known as idealized fractals and suffer from mathematical difficulties such as non-differentiability and non-homogeneity. But band limited finite fractal does not suffer from these mathematical difficulties and uses power-spectrum of roughness with band limited power law.

To get the physical insights, the moments of power-spectrum are used which is related to the mean square derivatives of surface profile. The 2j-th moments of power-spectrum is given as⁵³ :

$$\begin{aligned} m_{2j} &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \int d^2 K_{\parallel} K_{\parallel}^{2j} \langle |\hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{\parallel})|^2 \rangle = \\ &\langle (\nabla_{\parallel}^j \zeta(r_{\parallel}))^2 \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\nabla_{||}^j \equiv (\partial/\partial x, \partial/\partial y)$ is the two dimensional gradient operator. The moments of power-spectrum are related to the various morphological characteristics of a rough surface such as : the mean square (MS) width (m_0), the MS gradient (m_2) and the MS curvature (m_4) etc. SEM/AFM studies are used to get the surface roughness correlation function, power-spectrum and its various moments⁴⁸.

Theory of chronocoulometry for an EC' reaction mechanism at rough electrode-electrolyte interface

The concentration profile must be known around the arbitrary electrode profile to calculate the charge-transient for rough electrode-electrolyte interface. The concentration profile for an EC' reaction satisfies the diffusion equation as :

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \delta C_i(\vec{r}, t) = D_i \nabla^2 \delta C_i(\vec{r}, t) - k \delta C_i(\vec{r}, t), \quad (6)$$

where k is the pseudo first-order homogeneous rate constant, $i \equiv O, R$ and represents the oxidized or reduced species, respectively, $\delta C_i(\zeta)$ is the difference between surface and bulk concentration, D_i is diffusion-coefficient (for simplicity we assume $D_O = D_R = D$) and \vec{r} is the three dimensional vector, ($\vec{r} \equiv (x, y, z)$). In our calculation, we assume $\delta C(\vec{r}, t) = \delta C_O(\vec{r}, t) = -\delta C_R(\vec{r}, t)$. To complete the transformation of the boundary value problem to a simpler problem, we need to transform the initial and the bulk boundary problems. The transformed initial and bulk boundary problems are given as : $\delta C^*(\vec{r}, t = 0) = 0$ and $\delta C^*(\vec{r}_{||}, z \rightarrow \infty, t) = 0$. The surface boundary condition for both the processes (cathodic or anodic) are same. So, the transformed boundary condition is written as :

$$\delta C^*(\vec{r}, t) = -e^{kt} C_s^0 = -\frac{e^{kt} C_O^0}{1+\theta}, \quad (7)$$

where $\theta = \exp(-nf(E_i - E^{0'}))$, E_i and $E^{0'}$ are the initial and the formal potentials, respectively, $f = F/RT$, F is Faraday constant, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, C_O^0 is the bulk concentration of the oxidized species and n is the number of electron(s) involved in the first step redox reaction of

eq. (1).

The total charge at rough electrode-electrolyte interface can be related to the concentration profile by the following expression :

$$Q(t) = nFD \int_0^t dt' \int_{S_0} dS_0 \beta \partial_n \delta C_O(z = \zeta(\vec{r}_{||}), t'). \quad (8)$$

The concentration in the above equation (eq. (8)) is obtained as the perturbation solution upto second order in the surface profile. The concentration can be written in Fourier and Laplace transform domains for a fluctuating two-dimensional (2-D) rough surface as :

$$\delta C_O(\vec{K}_{||}, z, p) = \left(\frac{-C_s}{p} \right) \exp(-\tilde{q}_{||} z) \left\{ (2\pi)^2 \delta(\vec{K}_{||}) + q_k \hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{||}) + \frac{q_k^2}{2(2\pi)^2} \int dK'_{||} \hat{\zeta}(K'_{||} - \vec{K}_{||}) \hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{||}') \right. \\ \left. [2\tilde{\gamma}_{||, ||'} - 1] \right\} + O(\hat{\zeta}^3), \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{||})$ is the two dimensional Fourier transform of the rough surface profile given as :

$$\hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{||}) = \int dr_{||} e^{-j\vec{K}_{||} \cdot \vec{r}_{||}} \zeta(\vec{r}_{||}); j = \sqrt{-1} \\ q = (p/D)^{1/2} \\ q_k = [q^2 + k/D]^{1/2} \\ \tilde{q}_{||} = q_k \tilde{\gamma}_{||} = [q^2_k + \vec{K}_{||}^2]^{1/2} \\ \tilde{q}_{||, ||'} = q_k \tilde{\gamma}_{||, ||'} = [q^2_k + (\vec{K}_{||} - \vec{K}_{||}')^2]^{1/2}, \quad (10)$$

where κ is the homogeneous rate constant, $K_{||} = |\vec{K}_{||}|$ and $\delta(\vec{K}_{||})$ is the two-dimensional Dirac delta function in vector $\vec{K}_{||}$.

The expression for the total charge at rough electrode-electrolyte interface in the Laplace transform domain upto second order perturbation is given as :

$$Q(p) = \int_{S_0} d^2 r_{||} \left\{ [\hat{Q}_0 (2\pi)^2 \delta(\vec{K}_{||}) + \hat{Q}_1 \hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{||}) + \hat{Q}_2 \hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{||}') \hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{||} - \vec{K}_{||}')]; \vec{K}_{||} \rightarrow \vec{r}_{||} \right\}, \quad (11)$$

where p is the Laplace transform variable and $\int_{S_0} d^2r_{\parallel}(\cdot)$ is the integral over the xy plane, S_0 is the projection of the surface ζ on the reference surface $z = 0$. \hat{Q}_0 , \hat{Q}_1 and \hat{Q}_2 are the operators for the smooth surface, the first-order and the second-order terms in surface profile in Laplace transformed domain, respectively and are defined as :

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{Q}_0 &\equiv \frac{nFDC_s q_k}{p^2}; \hat{Q}_1 \equiv \hat{Q}_0(\tilde{q}_{\parallel} - q_k) \\ \hat{Q}_2 &\equiv \frac{nFDC_s}{(2\pi)^2 p^2} \int d^2K'_{\parallel} [\tilde{q}_{\parallel} \tilde{q}_{\parallel}'] \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} (q_k^2 + q_k \tilde{q}_{\parallel}) - (\vec{K}_{\parallel} - \vec{K}'_{\parallel})^2 \\ &\quad - \vec{K}'_{\parallel} \cdot (\vec{K}_{\parallel} - \vec{K}'_{\parallel})]. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Eq. (11) is used to predict the chronocoulometric response after taking the inverse Laplace transform and the inverse Fourier transform for a known surface profile. This expression provides insight into the response of a nanometer to micrometer scale structured electrode that has an arbitrary geometry profile or rough electrode with known profile.

The total charge-transient for a random surface morphology is obtained by taking the ensemble averaged charge-transient over all possible surface configurations. The ensemble averaged charge-transient has the information of surface morphology through the surface structure factor or power-spectrum of roughness. The Laplace transformed chronocoulometric response for the two dimensional statistically homogeneous random rough electrode is obtained by ensemble-averaging over all possible surface configurations on eq. (11) as :

$$\begin{aligned} \langle Q(p) \rangle &= \frac{nFA_0 DC_s q_k}{p^2} \left\{ 1 + \frac{q_k}{(2\pi)^2} \int \right. \\ &\quad \left. d^2K_{\parallel} [\tilde{q}_{\parallel} - q_k] \langle |\hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{\parallel})|^2 \rangle \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Above equation (eq. (13)) can be written in terms of

the Laplace transformed generalized Cottrell current^{53,55} ($\langle I_{gc}(p) \rangle$) for the rough electrode as :

$$\langle Q(p) \rangle = \frac{1}{p} \left(1 + \frac{k}{p} \right) \langle I_{gc}(p+k) \rangle \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle I_{gc}(p) \rangle &= \frac{nFA_0 DC_s}{q^2} \left\{ 1 + \frac{q}{(2\pi)^2} \int \right. \\ &\quad \left. d^2K_{\parallel} [q_{\parallel} - q] \langle |\hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{\parallel})|^2 \rangle \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The inverse Laplace transform of eq. (14) for pseudo first-order catalytic coupled reaction mechanism can be rearranged as :

$$\begin{aligned} \langle Q(t) \rangle &= \int_0^t dt \left\{ 1 + k \int_0^t dt \right\} e^{-kt} \langle I_{gc}(t) \rangle \\ &= \int_0^t dt \left\{ 1 + k \int_0^t dt \right\} e^{-kt} \frac{d}{dt} \langle Q_{ga}(t) \rangle \\ &= \left\{ 1 + k \int_0^t dt \right\}^2 e^{-kt} \langle Q_{ga}(t) \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\langle I_{gc}(t) \rangle = \frac{d}{dt} \langle Q_{ga}(t) \rangle$. Here $\langle Q_{ga}(t) \rangle$ is the total ensemble averaged charge transient when no chemical reaction takes place in the second step of the pseudo-first-order catalytic coupled reaction (see eq. (1)), known as generalized Anson equation⁷.

Equation (16) is the generalization of the Danckwerts' expression⁵⁶ in terms of the charge at rough electrode which is the first of its kind. It relates the charge-transients with coupled homogeneous reaction to the generalized Anson equation⁷ of rough electrode. The eq. (16) can be rearranged as :

$$\begin{aligned} \langle Q(t) \rangle &= e^{-kt} \langle Q_{ga}(t) \rangle + 2k \int_0^t dt' e^{-kt'} \langle Q_{ga}(t') \rangle + \\ &\quad k^2 \int_0^t dt' \int_0^{t'} dt'' e^{-kt''} \langle Q_{ga}(t'') \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Here $\langle Q(t) \rangle$ is the total ensemble averaged charge transient for the pseudo first-order catalytic coupled (EC') reaction mechanism. The second term in the curly bracket in eq. (16) introduces the kinetic effects of the EC' reaction. The eq. (17) is the extension of the Danckwerts' expression⁵⁶ in terms of the charge at rough electrode-electrolyte interface. The simplest Danckwerts' expression requires a linear time-independent operator while eq. (16) is valid for square of the operator. In the above eq. (16), $\{\cdot\}$ represents an operator. From eq. (17), it is clear that, it accounts the kinetics of the simple reversible redox reaction (pure Nernstian case) as well (first term). This extension of Danckwert's expression could prove useful in the study of an EC' reaction mechanism at rough electrode-electrolyte interface.

The quantity $\langle Q_{ga}(t) \rangle$ is the total ensemble averaged charge transient for purely diffusion-controlled reversible redox reaction and is given as⁷ :

$$\langle Q_{ga}(t) \rangle = \frac{2nFA_0C_s\sqrt{Dt}}{\sqrt{\pi}} (1 + \hat{R} \langle |\hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{||})|^2 \rangle), \quad (18)$$

where operator \hat{R} brings in dynamic effect of surface roughness on the charge through its action on power spectrum of roughness of electrode, given by

$$\hat{R} = -\frac{1}{2(2\pi)^2 Dt} \int d^2K_{||} (1 - \exp(-K_{||}^2 Dt) - \sqrt{\pi K_{||}^2 Dt} \operatorname{erf}(\sqrt{K_{||}^2 Dt})). \quad (19)$$

Chronocoulogram at finite self-affine fractal electrodes

The development of fractal geometry was a significant breakthrough in the description of irregularity present in the nature⁵⁷. The topography of a rough physical surface is often random but exhibits statistical self-resemblance over a range of scale because the random processes that formed the surface show the scale invariance^{57,58}. Such kind of surface or topography is described by using fractal geometry.

The fractal surfaces can be self-similar or self-affine in nature⁵⁷. The self-affine fractal surfaces are those surfaces in which the surface functions remain statistically invariant under scale transformation : $(x, y, z) \rightarrow (\lambda x, \lambda y, \lambda^H z)$ where H is the roughness Hurst's exponent. Hurst's exponent describes the persistence and anti-persistence behavior in the height fluctuation and is related to fractal dimension (D_H) as : $D_H = 3-H$ for isotropic self-affine surface.

Surfaces with limited scales of invariance property are usually described by the stationary Gaussian random processes with a power-law spectrum over a limited range of wave-numbers⁵⁹. The roughness spectrum of an approximately self-affine isotropic (random) fractal surface is described in terms of a limited band of wave-numbers ($\vec{K}_{||}$) which follows a power-law function as^{60,61} :

$$\langle |\hat{\zeta}(\vec{K}_{||})|^2 \rangle = \mu |K_{||}|^{2D_H-7}, \quad 1/L \leq |K_{||}| \leq 1/\ell, \quad (20)$$

The above expression (eq. (20)) of power-spectrum which is used to describe the roughness and consists of four physical characteristics. The four physical characteristics are fractal dimension (D_H) which is the global property of roughness and describes scale invariance property of the roughness. The lower cut-off length scale (ℓ) which is the length above which surface shows fractal behavior. Similarly, the upper cut-off length scale (L) is the length below which surface shows fractal behavior. The ratio, L/ℓ ($=\rho$), is known as range of fractality and it must be large enough to be a fractal surface. The fourth physical characteristics is the strength of fractality (μ) which is related to the topothesy of fractal⁶⁰⁻⁶² and $\mu \rightarrow 0$ means no roughness. It is related to the width of the interface through the topothesy length (ℓ_τ) as : $\mu = \ell_\tau^{2D_H-3}$. These realistic fractal characteristics can be obtained from AFM and SEM measurements on the surface and its power-spectrum⁴⁸. The idealized fractal description of anomalous power-law behavior in the charge-transient does not provide proper characterization since their time exponent is simply assumed

to be function of D_H only.

To get the physical insights into the rough surface morphology, the moments of power-spectrum are used. The moments of power-spectrum provide the physical quantities such as : mean square (MS) width of interface (m_0), MS gradient (m_2), MS curvature (m_4) and so on. The general expression for the $2j$ -th moment of the power-spectrum for a band-limited fractal can be written as⁶³ :

$$m_{2j} = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} \left(\frac{l^{-2(\delta+j)}}{\delta+j} - \frac{L^{-2(\delta+j)}}{\delta+j} \right), \quad (21)$$

where $\delta = D_H - 5/2$.

The quantitative measure of the roughness of the surface is obtained by knowing the roughness factor, R^* . This gives the extent of deviation of electrochemical responses (current, charge, absorbance, etc.) from the smooth surface. The roughness factor is related to MS gradient (m_2) obtained from moment of power-spectrum as discussed above. The rough surfaces with small m_2 has small μ also, which are referred as low roughness surfaces. The rough surfaces with large m_2 means large μ and has large roughness surfaces. The expression for the roughness factor for low roughness surfaces is given by $R^* \approx 1 + m_2$ similarly, the roughness factor for the large roughness surfaces is $R^* = \sqrt{\pi m_2/2}$.

The total interfacial ensemble averaged charge-transient for an EC' process is obtained by solving the eq. (17) which is the general form of the charge-transient for rough electrode surfaces. Thus, the first term of the eq. (17) is the ensemble averaged charge-transient for the purely diffusion-limited reaction at an approximately self-affine fractal electrode surface, takes the form as⁷ :

$$\langle Q_{ga}(t) \rangle = Q_P(t) (1 - R_{F1}(t) + R_{F2}(t, \ell) - R_{F2}(t, L))$$

$$R_{F1}(t) = -\frac{m_0}{2Dt} + \left(\frac{\mu}{8\pi(Dt)^{D_H-3/2}} \right)$$

$$\Gamma(D_H - 5/2, Dt/\ell^2, Dt/L^2),$$

$$R_{F2}(t, \lambda) = \frac{\mu}{8\pi(D_H - 2)\lambda^{2D_H-3}\sqrt{t^*}}$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erf}(\sqrt{t^*}) - t^{*2-D_H} \gamma(D_H - 3/2, t^*) \right), \quad (22)$$

where λ is the cut-off length (either ℓ or L) and dimensionless time $t^* = \frac{Dt}{\lambda^2}$, $\Gamma(\alpha, x_0, x_1) = \Gamma(\alpha, x_0) - \Gamma(\alpha, x_1) = \gamma(\alpha, x_1) - \gamma(\alpha, x_0)$, $\Gamma(\alpha, x_i)$ and $\gamma(\alpha, x_i)$ are the incomplete Gamma functions³⁰. The eq. (22) represents the exact form of the charge⁷ because the first term of eq. (17) can be integrated with respect to time. The second and the third terms of eq. (17) has difficulty to integrate with respect to the time with the exact form. This is due to the fact that these terms bring the kinetic contributions. Thus, to solve these two terms, an approximated form of the charge is used to overcome this difficulty for longer time. The longer time is the kinetic control and this approximation works good for the longer time regime. So we use this approximation to solve the second and the third terms of eq. (17). The expression for the approximate form of the charge used to solve these two terms is given as⁷ :

$$\langle Q_{ga}(t) \rangle \approx \frac{2nFA_0C_s\sqrt{Dt}}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left(1 - \frac{\mu\ell^{-2\delta}}{8\pi\delta Dt} + \frac{\mu\Gamma(\delta)}{8\pi(2\delta+1)(Dt)^{\delta+1}} \right). \quad (23)$$

The above eq. (23) is valid for $t \gg t_i$, where t_i is the inner fractal crossover time. It is the time after which the anomalous intermediate time regime is observed in the charge-transient.

The short-time contribution to the total charge-transient, i.e. $\langle Q(t_i) \rangle$ is very small for all $t \gg t_i$. Hence, it is ignored in the above calculation.

After using eq. (23), the second term (say, $Q_1(t)$) in the eq. (17) takes the form as :

$$Q_1(t) = 2k \int_0^t dt' e^{-kt'} \langle Q_{ga}(t') \rangle$$

$$= \frac{2k(2nFA_0C_s\sqrt{Dt})}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erf}(\sqrt{kt})}{2\sqrt{k^3}} - \frac{\sqrt{t} e^{-kt}}{k} \right. \\ \left. - \frac{\mu \ell^{-2\delta} \sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erf}(\sqrt{kt})}{8\pi\delta D\sqrt{k}} \right. \\ \left. - \frac{\mu\Gamma(\delta)k^{\delta-1/2}\Gamma(1/2-\delta, kt)}{8\pi(2\delta+1)D^{\delta+1}} \right\} \quad (24)$$

and the third term (say, $Q_2(t)$) in the eq. (17) for self-affine fractal electrode becomes as :

$$Q_2(t) = k^2 \int_0^t dt' \int_0^{t'} dt'' e^{-kt''} \langle Q_{ga}(t'') \rangle \\ = \frac{k^2(2nFA_0C_s\sqrt{D})}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erf}(\sqrt{kt})}{2\sqrt{k^3}} - \left(\frac{-3}{2k} + t \right) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{3\sqrt{t} e^{-kt}}{2k^2} - \frac{\mu}{8\pi D\sqrt{k}} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi} \ell^{-2\delta}}{\delta} \left(\frac{\sqrt{t} e^{-kt}}{\sqrt{\pi k}} \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \left(t - \frac{1}{2k} \right) \operatorname{erf}(\sqrt{kt}) \right) + \frac{\Gamma(\delta)k^\delta}{(2\delta+1)D^\delta} \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. \left(t\Gamma(1/2-\delta, kt) - \frac{1}{k} \Gamma(3/2-\delta, kt) \right) \right) \right\}. \quad (25)$$

For the limiting case that is, at $k = 0$ the second and the third terms in the eq. (17) becomes zero and eq. (17) is reduced to purely generalized Anson equation⁷. Under this condition, the eq. (17) becomes same as eq. (18) in Ref. 7. Thus we can say that, eq. (17) is also valid for the simple reversible redox systems (purely Nernstian case) under the limiting case. If the roughness is zero this equation becomes Anson equation for planar case (eq. (3)). The differentiation of eq. (17) with respect to the time will give current. Hence, the differential form of eq. (17) is the chronoamperometric (current-time relationship) response for an EC' reaction mechanism at rough elec-

trode-electrolyte interface. Thus, eq. (17) provides more physical insights into the EC' reaction mechanism with proper characterization of rough electrode-electrolyte interface in terms of fractal morphological characteristics.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 depicts the various morphological and phenomenological characteristics which control the chronocoulometric responses of an EC' reaction mechanism at fractally rough electrode-electrolyte interface. As discussed earlier, the four morphological characteristics are fractal dimension (D_H), strength of fractality (μ), lower (ℓ) and upper (L) cut-off length scales. Out of these, D_H , μ and ℓ contribute strongly to the chronocoulometric responses while L shows weak dependency for large fractal range, ρ ($= L/\ell$ ratio).

In Fig. 2, the effect of fractal dimension on charge-transient for an EC' reaction mechanism taking place at a rough electrode-electrolyte interface is analyzed. Since, fractal dimension is the global property of the rough surface thus, the increase in the fractal dimension means increase in the roughness or fractal nature of the surface. The double logarithmic plot of charge and time clearly demonstrates that, as the fractal dimension increases, the charge-transients correspondingly enhance. The fractal rough surface has more effective area and due to the fractal nature of the surface the reaction taking place at the surface becomes more localized. As the roughness increases, the localized reaction becomes more and more prominent which increases the generation of the redox species even more at the electrode surface. Thus, charge-transient enhances significantly, if the fractal nature of the rough surface increases. The first plot from bottom is generated by using eq. (2) which is the planar catalytic response.

The two time regimes can be seen easily in the double logarithmic plot of charge and time, i.e. anomalous intermediate and long-time regimes. The inter-

Fig. 2. Effect of fractal dimension (D_H) on charge-transients for an EC' reaction mechanism taking place at a rough electrode-electrolyte interface. The values of D_H are taken as : 2.10, 2.15, 2.20, 2.25. The other parameters are taken as : $\ell = 30$ nm, $L = 5$ μ m, $\mu = 10^{-5}$ (a.u.), $k = 1$ s $^{-1}$, $C_s = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ mol cm $^{-3}$, $D = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ cm 2 s $^{-1}$, $A_0 = 0.15$ cm 2 , $n = 1$.

mediate-time regime shows anomalous power law behavior and is dependent on fractal morphological characteristics. There is very weak dependency of the kinetics in this region and gives the information about the surface morphology. Thus, anomalous intermediate-time regime provides the information about the fractal nature of the rough electrode surface. The long-time regime is the time dependent kinetic controlled.

Fig. 3 depicts the effect of strength of fractality on charge-transient. The strength of fractality is related to the width of the interface through topothesy length, ℓ_τ . The larger width of the interface leads to the more rough surface. The increase in the strength of fractality, enhances the charge-transients due to increase in the width of the interface hence, roughness of the surface. The double logarithmic plot of charge and time clearly demonstrates the two time regimes in it. That is, the anomalous intermediate and long time regimes.

Fig. 3. Effect of strength of fractality (μ) on charge-transients. The values of μ (a.u.) are taken as : μ_0 , $2 \times \mu_0$, $4 \times \mu_0$, $8 \times \mu_0$ where $\mu_0 = 10^{-6}$. The other parameters are taken as : $D_H = 2.2$, $\ell = 30$ nm; $L = 5$ μ m; $k = 1$ s $^{-1}$, $C_s = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ mol cm $^{-3}$, $D = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ cm 2 s $^{-1}$, $A_0 = 0.15$ cm 2 , $n = 1$.

The intermediate-time regime shows weak dependency of strength of fractality with time. Finally, it merges with planar response in the long-time regime. The first plot from bottom is of planar catalytic response (eq. (2)).

In Fig. 4, the effect of lower cut-off length scale on charge-transient is analyzed. The decrease in the lower cut-off length scale increases the self-affine fractal nature of the rough-surface. Due to decrease in the lower cut-off length scale, roughness of the surface increases which enhances the charge-transient. Here it is important to understand the relationship between the lower cut-off length scale and the inner-transition time (t_i). The inner-transition time is the time after which the anomalous intermediate-time regime is started. The short-time domain is strongly dependent on lower cut-off length scale while long-time domain is controlled by width of the interface (h). The width of the interface is a strong function of upper cut-off length scale (L) and has no impact of

Fig. 4. Effect of lower cut-off length scale (ℓ) on charge-transients while other parameters are kept constant. The values of ℓ (nm) are taken as : 15, 30, 60, 200. The other parameters are as : $D_H = 2.2$, $\mu = 10^{-5}$ (a.u.), $L = 5 \mu\text{m}$, $k = 1 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $C_s = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol cm}^{-3}$, $D = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $A_0 = 0.15 \text{ cm}^2$, $n = 1$.

lower cut-off length scale in the long-time domain. Therefore, the inner transition-time decreases with decrease in the lower cut-off length scale while it increases as the lower cut-off length increases. To observe the roughness effect, the diffusion layer width must be comparable to the surface irregularities. We are interested to observe the roughness in the time region of 10^{-3} s to 10 s. The value of the inner-transition time is often much less than 10^{-3} s, below 10^{-3} s the double-layer region becomes prominent and causes an additional effect on the charge-transient. The magnitude of double-layer charging with ohmic drop can be corrected in the experimental data as reported in the recent publication⁶⁴.

Fig. 5 shows the effect of kinetics (homogeneous rate constant) of the EC' reaction mechanism on charge-transient at rough electrode-electrolyte interface. From Fig. 5 it is clear that, as the value of homogeneous rate constant increases, first it shows no (especially at the lower values) or weak depen-

Fig. 5. Effect of homogeneous rate constant (k) on charge-transients while keeping other morphological characteristics are constant. The values of k (s^{-1}) are taken as : 5, 30, 60, 100, 250. The other parameters are taken as : $D_H = 2.2$, $\mu = 10^{-5}$ (a.u.), $\ell = 30 \text{ nm}$, $L = 5 \mu\text{m}$, $C_s = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol cm}^{-3}$, $D = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $A_0 = 0.15 \text{ cm}^2$, $n = 1$. The inset plot represents the traditional $Q(t) \text{ vs } t^{1/2}$ plot.

dency on charge-transient. It becomes plateau and after that enhances rapidly in the long-time regime. This plateau becomes more and more prominent as the value of the rate constant increases. At significantly larger value of rate constant, initially the charge-transient decreases slightly and then increases rapidly in the long time regime. The time at which this rapid increase in charge-transient is observed, keep on decreasing as the rate constant increases and is roughly corresponds to $1/k$ value. In the early time, there is no effect of the rate constant. Anomalous intermediate-time regime shows very weak dependency on rate constant. But the long-time domain shows strong dependency of rate constant on charge-transients. This clearly demonstrates that the long time regime is time dependent kinetic controlled regime. The rapid increase of charge-transient in the long time regime is due to the catalytically coupled reaction. The inset is the traditional plot ($Q(t) \text{ vs } t^{1/2}$) of the corresponding

curves. There are no characteristic features observed in this presentation as the double logarithmic curves provide. Thus, we can observe the roughness effect clearly in the double logarithmic scale while it is not seen in the traditional plots.

Conclusions

In summary, a theoretical model for single potential step charge-transients for pseudo first-order catalytic coupled reaction (EC') mechanism at the rough electrode-electrolyte interface is developed. The theory presented here uses approach based on the power spectrum of roughness and addresses the detail analysis of chronocoulometric response for the finite fractal electrode roughness. The important conclusions are as follows : (i) the charge-transient response enhances with the increase in the surface roughness, (ii) the fractal nature of the rough surfaces shows enhanced charge-transient with increase in fractal dimension, topothesy length and decrease in the minute scale of fractality, (iii) anomalous intermediate-time regime shows strong dependency on these fractal characteristics, (iv) the long-time regime is bulk kinetic controlled, (v) the time window available for Nernstian or diffusion control regime in EC' reaction is $D/k^2 < t < k^{-1}$. Hence, large value of D/k^2 will curtail the Nernstian regime in EC' reaction, (vi) the influence of roughness will be maximum for the smaller grain size (ℓ) while the width of roughness (ℓ_r) is greater than $\sqrt{D/k}$. Finally, the roughness enhances sensitivity to EC' reaction.

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